

Can CRISPR Improve Forensic Investigations?

Independent Research Paper by Maya Younis

Abstract

The development of CRISPR-Cas technology has significantly transformed the world of genomics, gene editing, and forensic science. This paper explores the potential applications of CRISPR within the field of forensic science, including its role in advancing the process of human identification, improving the analysis of degraded DNA, and assisting in genetic phenotyping. It also considers the applications of CRISPR in environmental and wildlife forensics. Lastly, this paper mentions the ethical and societal debates of CRISPR applications and public debate about its usages in crime scene investigations.

What is CRISPR?

Few scientific breakthroughs have revolutionized biology like CRISPR-Cas. CRISPR, short for ‘clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats’, is a natural bacterial immune system that has been adapted into a revolutionary genome editing system. Genome editing involves the alteration of DNA sequences to change gene function or physical traits.

Originally, CRISPR was discovered as a natural immune system in bacteria that stores invading viral DNA as a memory of past infections to stop future infections. Using these specific memories, the CRISPR-Cas system has the ability to cut new infections. Scientists discovered this and thus began researching other potential applications for CRISPR’s precise cutting mechanism.

CRISPR-Cas works using proteins called nucleases, which are essentially used for their ability to target and cut specific areas of DNA. Cas genes within CRISPR sequences code for these nucleases. These genes are part of the immune system that have the ability to cut out pieces of the genome; therefore, the CRISPR-Cas9 system was specifically identified as a means to *precisely* target and cut parts of the DNA in any organism, or in other words, edit genes. CRISPR-Cas9 exists among other variants of Cas, providing extensive opportunities.

The new technology is affordable, accessible, and fast, revolutionizing genome editing and making it more practical than ever before. Having brought a multitude of new possibilities into the world of genetic studies, medicine, and agriculture through its creation, it has brought reality into the long-researched idea of genome editing. As researchers suggest, CRISPR-Cas9 is an inexpensive, practical mechanism and provides a solid introduction into the world of modern-day gene engineering and editing (Polcz and Lewis).

Thinking futuristically, could CRISPR-Cas have other possibilities and applications to forensic science? This paper explores CRISPR's potential and challenges in forensic science.

The Potential Applications of CRISPR in Forensics

CRISPR-Cas offers many possibilities for the future of forensic science and specifically crime scene investigations. One of the most notable and famous applications is the potential of CRISPR-Cas9 to improve the accuracy of human identification by enhancing DNA profiling methods and using degraded DNA samples to overcome limitations from compromised evidence. DNA profiling relies on Short Tandem Repeats (STRs), which are repetitive DNA sequences that vary between individuals. According to a 2024 article on CRISPR-Cas9 exploration in forensic science, there is potential for CRISPR-Cas9 to help DNA profiling due to its ability to precisely

amplify STRs (Ullah Khan 6). CRISPR-Cas9 can aid in analysing microsatellites (also short repeating DNA sequences), which are essentially STRs themselves. STR-Seq – an emerging method in human genome sequencing – is a kind of next-generation sequencing technology that employs CRISPR-Cas9-targeted fragmentation for accurate amplification and analysis of DNA microsatellite sequences (Liu et al.). This could be a promising advancement for forensic scientists and their work in accurate DNA profiling. Similarly, forensic scientists will likely make advancements in DNA profiling by using CRISPR-Cas technologies to analyze degraded DNA. The CRISPR-Cas enzymes Cas9 and Cas12a create double-stranded breaks, which are then repaired by the mechanisms of the cell itself (Cubbon, Ivancic-Bace, and Bolt). This interplay between CRISPR-Cas and cellular DNA repair processes may be useful for investigations because under the pressure of controlled and, importantly, *precise* breaks by Cas systems, the affected cells could reconstruct or repair damaged DNA segments, helping produce clearer genetic profiles.

Aside from the types of human identification tools in forensics work already discussed (DNA profiling and degraded DNA analysis), another important consideration for the potential of CRISPR-Cas9 is its future uses in phenotyping. Phenotyping in the setting of forensics work is to make biological predictions regarding the physical traits of an individual based on their DNA. The same 2024 article discusses the possibility of using CRISPR-Cas9 in examining the presence or absence of specific genetic markers within DNA – these markers, which are linked to physical traits, can be detected or targeted using CRISPR-Cas9 technology. Though CRISPR-Cas9 is primarily a gene-editing tool, it can be highly useful for targeting and identifying markers. Depending on the function of these markers detected by CRISPR-Cas9, forensic scientists can make phenotypic predictions in criminal investigations.

Beyond its applications in human identification, CRISPR could also revolutionize the way environmental and wildlife crimes are investigated. Environmental and wildlife forensics are promising fields for CRISPR-Cas systems in the future. These systems may be useful in identifying species that are subjected to illegal activities such as trade or hunting. Due to its high specificity, Cas systems could determine the origin of materials at crime scenes (animal tissue, hair, blood, and environmental DNA) by targeting species-specific DNA sequences and using their precision to observe relevant genetic markers (Ullah Khan 7). CRISPR-Cas12a, a CRISPR system that is highly functional in precise identification, can detect dangerous pathogens and analyze environmental samples to link individual species to pathogens in their habitats (Sobral, Dinis-Oliveira, and Barbosa). While it may seem that CRISPR-Cas systems aren't necessary in these settings, and that traditional DNA sequencing or PCR (polymerase chain reaction) methods could oversee these kinds of identifications, there are actually many limitations – CRISPR systems offer more precision in identifying species, especially in natural settings where DNA is more likely to degrade and can become muddled easier. Additionally, CRISPR can detect pathogens that affect wildlife, a capability usually absent among traditional forensic and identification techniques.

Ethical Considerations

With the introduction of breakthrough technology like CRISPR-Cas systems, there are, of course, considerations beyond scientific advancement including ethical and societal impacts. A 2020 article emphasizes the need for balanced global legislation: “In order for CRISPR-Cas9 to be used safely in all areas and to solve potential issues, worldwide legislation should be prepared, taking into account the opinions of both life and social scientists, policy makers, and all other stakeholders of the sectors, and CRISPR-Cas9 applications should be implemented

according to such legislations. However, these controls should not restrict scientific freedom” (Ayanoglu, Elcin, and Elcin). A major topic of discussion among scientists, especially forensic scientists, are the circumstances of societal opinions and privacy issues. For many, CRISPR usage raises significant privacy concerns as well as worries regarding misuse of genetic data or unauthorized editing. Especially in the world of forensics, where unauthorized or mistaken editing for crime investigations could lead to errors in identifying suspects or evidence, CRISPR usage could become a future issue. When collecting DNA samples in crime scenes, the possibility of issues regarding consent and the use of gene data without familial or individual consent are everlasting. A specific example of the bioethical issues involving genetic data usage in a real-world case is the Golden State Killer Case – the case was cold for forty years before investigators used information in a genealogy database for long-lost relatives. Though investigators were able to solve the case using the DNA of a relative of the killer in the database to find the suspect’s genetic profile and matching it to a DNA sample of the suspect, the methods used in the case significantly upset the public. “People who upload their DNA to genealogy websites such as the one in question have consented to have their genetic information used for a very specific purpose – to find relatives. They have not given consent for this information to be used by the police” (Leonard). With this concern of consent also comes issues of biosecurity – people worry about misuse or malicious intent of this same kind of access to databases. CRISPR applications, which may also stir up issues regarding breaches of privacy due to their involvement in human genome database information, must be approached with caution in the future until its implications become clearer.

So, What does the Future of CRISPR Hold?

The future of CRISPR creates many possibilities for forensic scientists. Among these possibilities are identification advancements, such as more precise DNA profiling/fingerprinting, easier analysis of degraded DNA, phenotyping with DNA samples, and higher possibilities within environmental/wildlife forensics. The future of CRISPR-Cas systems holds many opportunities, most involving higher levels of precision in DNA sequence analysis. However, as the usage of CRISPR-Cas systems become more widely used, especially in situations involving law and crime (such as the forensics field), it is possible for conflict to quickly appear and privacy issues to arise. I think that CRISPR-Cas would provide for useful integrations within forensic science applications, but safeguards are essential in order to avoid mass backlash against its use.

Ultimately, CRISPR's incorporation into forensic science could redefine the future of investigations and research, but we must take precautions, as the benefits may mean little if the ethical costs outweigh them.

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